

Mitral Insufficiency Secondary to Mitral Valve Prolapse Due to Barlow's Disease: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Barlow's disease is a common cause of primary degenerative mitral regurgitation. We present the case of a 61-year-old man with palpitations, dyspnea, and progressive fatigue. Echocardiography revealed an 11 mm mitral annular disjunction, bileaflet prolapse, posterior leaflet flail, and severe eccentric mitral regurgitation. After evaluation by the Heart Team, mitral valve replacement was indicated. Multimodal imaging enables adequate anatomical characterization and therapeutic planning, facilitating timely intervention and improving prognosis.

KEYWORDS: Barlow's disease, prolapse, regurgitation, surgical replacement, valve repair.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
20 March 2026

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

I. INTRODUCTION

In 1963, John Brereton Barlow defined a condition in which one or both leaflets of the mitral valve protrude into the left atrium during the systolic phase, describing it as valvular prolapse. On physical examination, it is identified as a late systolic murmur; this finding was attributed to Barlow based on his descriptions. This condition may be found in syndromes such as Marfan syndrome, Ehlers-Danlos syndrome, and osteogenesis imperfecta, among others. Primary mitral valve prolapse presents with myxomatous degeneration of the mitral valve, with prolapse toward the left atrium, occurring in isolation in most cases. Secondary mitral valve prolapse refers to the movement of one or both leaflets toward the left atrium during systole and is attributed to hypertrophic, ischemic, or rheumatic cardiomyopathies (2).

II. CASE PRESENTATION

A 61-year-old male patient began follow-up in June 2025 after being referred to the clinical cardiology service of our unit due to palpitations, vertigo, dyspnea, and fatigue, symptoms that worsen with physical exertion. On physical examination, a grade IV/VI holosystolic murmur was detected at the mitral area with radiation to the axillary fossa. A color Doppler echocardiogram was requested due to suspicion of mitral regurgitation. The study reported a mitral valve without annular dilation; however, an 11 mm mitral annular disjunction was observed, with thickened leaflets and

the presence of 5 mm mitral prolapse involving both leaflets, as well as a posterior leaflet flail, resulting in severe eccentric mitral regurgitation. A medical-surgical meeting with the Heart Team was held in October 2025, concluding with the indication for mitral valve replacement. The patient is currently awaiting the surgical date.

Figura 1: Transthoracic echocardiogram showing: A) mitral annular disjunction and posterior leaflet flail. B) color Doppler mode with a mitral regurgitation jet. C) Pickelhaube sign on tissue Doppler. D) M-mode showing a jet during the late systolic phase.

III. DISCUSSION

Mitral regurgitation is classified according to the severity of the clinical presentation as acute or chronic. Acute mitral regurgitation is attributed to papillary muscle rupture or rupture of the chordae tendineae due to ST-elevation acute myocardial infarction or trauma, leaflet perforation due to infective endocarditis, or spontaneous rupture of the chordae tendineae associated with degenerative leaflets due to myxomatous degenerative prolapse and Marfan syndrome. Chronic mitral regurgitation is subdivided into primary and secondary; primary causes are degenerative, whereas secondary causes are attributed to left ventricular dilation due to ischemic and non-ischemic etiologies.

Barlow's disease is still of unknown etiology. Genetically, a mutation in a gene on chromosome 16p11.2 with autosomal dominant inheritance has been investigated, with additional findings in the valve, leaflets, and annulus such as leaflet thickening, multiple myxomatous scallops, abnormal, elongated and thickened chordae, and even ruptured chordae (3). Barlow's disease has been described since the 1960s and is considered the second most frequent surgical indication in cardiovascular surgery services, with valve repair being the technique of choice. Its prevalence in the 60–80 year age range is 21.3%; 14.3% in primary mitral regurgitation and 7% in secondary mitral regurgitation. It is a disease more common in adults, particularly in women between 30 and 60 years of age. The rate of sudden death is approximately 0.2–0.4% per year in patients with prolapse (1).

Barlow syndrome has a broad clinical spectrum ranging from asymptomatic patients to the presence of nonspecific chest pain, palpitations secondary to supraventricular and ventricular extrasystoles, signs of decompensated heart failure, atrial fibrillation, and embolic events. On physical examination, a mid-systolic or late systolic click may be auscultated together with a late systolic murmur, which is suggestive of mitral valve prolapse (4).

The electrocardiogram may show repolarization abnormalities such as T-wave inversion, ST-segment alterations, QT interval prolongation, and ventricular extrasystoles. These findings occur in up to one third of patients with Barlow syndrome and, although uncommon, are associated with a risk of sudden death (5).

The initial diagnostic study is transthoracic echocardiography, which allows detection of mitral valve prolapse, assessment of its severity, and evaluation of its impact on left ventricular dynamics. In Barlow disease, annular dilation with redundant valvular tissue is identified, together with prolapse of multiple leaflet segments and/or protrusion of one or both leaflets. Mitral valve prolapse is characterized by abnormal systolic motion with posterior displacement of the mitral leaflet at the end of systole. The movement of the valve toward the left atrium may adopt a saddle-shaped configuration and exceed >2 mm beyond the mitral annulus. Other echocardiographic features include

asymmetry, involvement of both leaflets, and leaflet thickening of 3–5 mm (6).

Cardiac magnetic resonance imaging is considered the study of choice for quantifying ventricular volumes and mass and determining the ejection fraction. It provides three-dimensional analysis, assists in the characterization of the mitral valve, and determines the severity of mitral regurgitation when echocardiographic results are inconclusive (7).

In Barlow disease, since it represents a primary mitral regurgitation, the indications for intervention are well established. Surgery is the procedure of choice and is indicated for patients with symptoms attributable to mitral regurgitation, regardless of ventricular function. In asymptomatic patients, surgery is indicated in those presenting left ventricular dysfunction, defined as LVEF $\leq 60\%$, LVESD ≥ 40 mm, or LVESDi ≥ 20 mm/m² (8).

Furthermore, there is currently evidence of a potential mortality reduction benefit in asymptomatic patients with preserved ventricular function but with indexed left atrial volume ≥ 60 mL/m² or diameter ≥ 55 mm, atrial fibrillation, resting pulmonary artery systolic pressure > 50 mmHg, and concomitant moderate or severe secondary tricuspid regurgitation (9,10).

Current clinical guidelines recommend mitral valve repair over replacement, based on data from the MIDA registry (Mitral Regurgitation International Database), a multicenter registry that analyzed prognosis after repair and replacement. The results favored mitral valve repair, demonstrating lower operative mortality, better long-term survival, and fewer complications related to the mitral valve (11).

Surgical repair of the mitral valve in Barlow disease presents challenging characteristics that predispose to long-term dysfunction. These include leaflet undulations, which make it difficult for the surgeon to identify a normal reference point, thereby complicating the analysis and planning of the repair. Other challenging features include valvular prolapse, excess valvular tissue, and atrial displacement secondary to mitral leaflet insertion, which may lead to leaflet hypermobility and subsequent excessive myxoid degeneration (12).

Despite these challenges, multiple mitral valve repair techniques have been developed for Barlow disease—such as triangular resection, chordal shortening, chordal transfer, edge-to-edge repair, and posterior papillary muscle repositioning—which provide excellent long-term outcomes, with successful repair rates of up to 95% and freedom from reoperation at ten years of 96% (13).

The largest reported case series corresponds to the work of David and collaborators, who reviewed the outcomes of 701 patients with mitral prolapse, of whom 250 underwent surgery for bileaflet prolapse, including cases of Barlow disease. In this series, 80% of patients remained free from moderate or severe mitral regurgitation at 12 years (14).

CONCLUSIONS

Barlow disease continues to be one of the presentations of primary mitral regurgitation that requires the greatest diagnostic precision. In addition to its significant incidence in the adult population, it represents one of the most frequent causes requiring cardiovascular surgical care, with mitral valve repair being the preferred technique for its management.

Its evaluation represents a diagnostic challenge, and echocardiographic findings constitute the initial tool to determine the characteristics of the valvular apparatus, the severity of the disease, and its hemodynamic complications. However, this method may present limitations; therefore, it is ideal to complement it with other imaging studies, such as cardiac magnetic resonance imaging, which has demonstrated superiority in defining the characteristics of the mitral valve, as well as in the quantification of ventricular volumes and measurement of ventricular mass

Among the aspects to consider in patients with advanced stages of the disease is the remodeling of the left cardiac chambers, which translates into clinical impact reflected in the patient's functional status and associated comorbidities. A large number of patients seek medical care when they are already in NYHA functional class III–IV or present a significant history of atrial fibrillation.

Early mitral valve repair has shown important advances in correcting and slowing the progression of Barlow disease, reducing mortality and improving long-term survival free from complications and/or hospitalizations related to heart failure. The main challenge lies in early identification of patients at risk of developing this condition. This case confirms that identifying the anatomical characteristics described in Barlow disease contributes to reducing patient mortality through the planning of timely intervention.

REFERENCES

- I. Morales, C. A., Escalera, A., Salmerón, C., Hernández-Vaquero, D., Álvarez, R., Díaz, R., Mencía, P., Callejo, F., Llosa, J. C., Meana, B., Zabala, M., Morales, A., & Silva, J. A. (2022). Insuficiencia mitral en la enfermedad de Barlow. La mirada desde la reparación. *Cirugía Cardiovascular*, 29, S68-S73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.circv.2021.12.006>
- II. Rosas-Munive E, Valenzuela-Flores GA, Valenzuela-Flores AA. Prolapso valvular mitral. Revisión de la literatura. *Cir Cir*. 2004;72(5):415-420.
- III. Chaudhari SS, Chokkalingam Mani B. Insuficiencia de la válvula mitral. En: *StatPearls* [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025.
- IV. Pérez-Vázquez, S. I., Ladewig-Bernaldez, G. I., González-Trueba, E. F., Mondragón-Morales, J., Hernández-Jiménez, M. G., García-Pérez, L. A., & Martínez-Guzmán, A. (2023). Barlow syndrome: a diagnostic difficulty. *Revista Médica del Hospital General de México*, 86(3). <https://doi.org/10.24875/hgmx.22000079>
- V. Hernández-Vaquero, D., Díaz, R., & Silva, J. (2015). Peor supervivencia a largo plazo después de cirugía coronaria sin circulación extracorpórea que con ella. *Cirugía Cardiovascular*, 23(1), 59-60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.circv.2015.08.003>
- VI. Rayudu NV. Mitral valve prolapse. *Apollo Med*. 2018;15:11-4.
- VII. Wijngaarden, A. L. van, Kruithof, B. P. T., Vinella, T., Barge-Schaapveld, D. Q. C. M., & Marsan, N. A. (2021). Characterization of degenerative mitral valve disease: differences between fibroelastic deficiency and Barlow's disease. *Journal Of Cardiovascular Development And Disease*, 8(2). doi:10.3390/jcdd8020023
- VIII. Suri RM, Vanoverschelde JL, Grigioni F, Schaff HV, Tribouilloy C, Avierinos JF, et al. Association between early surgical intervention vs watchful waiting and outcomes for mitral regurgitation due to flail mitral valve leaflets. *JAMA*. 2013;310:609-16.
- IX. Butcher SC, Essayagh B, Steyerberg EW, Benfari G, Antoine C, Grigioni F, et al. Factors influencing post-surgical survival in degenerative mitral regurgitation. *Eur Heart J*. 2023;44:871-81.
- X. Grigioni F, Clavel MA, Vanoverschelde JL, Tribouilloy C, Pizarro R, Huebner M, et al. The MIDA mortality risk score: development and external validation of a prognostic model for early and late death in degenerative mitral regurgitation. *Eur Heart J*. 2018;39:1281-91.
- XI. Kavsur, R., Spieker, M., Iliadis, C., Metzke, C., Transier, M., Tiyerili, V., Horn, P., Baldus, S., Kelm, M., Nickenig, G., Westenfeld, R., Pfister, R., Becher, M. U., & Rhineland, O. T. H. F. N. (2021). Mitral Regurgitation International Database (MIDA) Score Predicts Outcome in Patients With Heart Failure Undergoing Transcatheter Edge-to-Edge Mitral Valve Repair. *Journal Of The American Heart Association*, 10(13), e019548. <https://doi.org/10.1161/jaha.120.019548>
- XII. Hutchins, G. M., Moore, G. W., & Skoog, D. K. (1986). The Association of Floppy Mitral Valve with Disjunction of the Mitral Annulus Fibrosus. *New England Journal Of Medicine*, 314(9), 535-540. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejm198602273140902>
- XIII. Borger, M. A., & Mohr, F. W. (2010). Repair of Bileaflet Prolapse in Barlow Syndrome. *Seminars In Thoracic And Cardiovascular Surgery*, 22(2), 174-178. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.semctvs.2010.09.006>
- XIV. David, T. E., Ivanov, J., Armstrong, S., Christie, D., & Rakowski, H. (2005). A comparison of outcomes of mitral valve repair for degenerative disease with

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posterior, anterior, and bileaflet prolapse. *Journal Of Thoracic And Cardiovascular Surgery*, 130(5), 1242-1249.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtcvs.2005.06.046>